

Functional Assays for Solute Carrier Transporters

Biosensor transport assay for SLC1A3 using HEK293-SLC1A3- WTOE cells

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Assay description

This assay detects aspartate uptake using a biosensor for aspartate, cyto-iAspSnFR (Addgene #201394) in HEK293-JumpIn-TRex cells overexpressing SLC1A3. Aspartate uptake leads in an increased emission in the GFP channel that is normalized to the red fluorescent protein mScarlet-I for expression level normalization. Fluorescence detection is performed using a flow cytometer for increased throughput and high cell number statistics.

Assay protocol

2 Mio cells (HEK293-JumpIn-TRex-SLC1A3-WTOE-p1) were seeded in 10mL full medium (refers to 10% FCS (Gibco #10500064)/DMEM high-glucose, pyruvate, glutamax, phenolred Gibco #31966021), supplemented with 1 µg/mL doxycycline to induce SLC1A3 expression. The following day, the cells were transfected with cyto-iAspSnFR using Lipofectamine 3000 (Thermofisher) according to the manufacturer's instructions, using the following amounts: 20 µg DNA, 40 µL P3000, 30 µL R3000, 500+500 µL OptiMEM). The following day, cells were starved for ~5-6 hours in 10% dialyzed FCS/DMEM (-glucose - pyruvate -glutamax). Cells were harvested by brief trypsinization, then taking cells in suspension in 10 mL of starvation medium. Cells were centrifugated, and taken up in 10% dia. FCS/PBS. For the assay, 100 µL cells suspension was combined with 100 µL PBS containing amino acids and test compounds. Cells were incubated for 30 min at r.t. (22 °C) before measurement was initialized at a BD Fortessa X-20 flow cytometer equipped with an HTS module. Optical configuration: sfGFP/FITC Ex 488 nm Em 530/30nm, mScarlet-I/PE-Texas Red Ex 561 nm, Em 610/20 nm. 80-100 µL were injected per sample and all events were recorded and stored for subsequent analysis in FlowJo 10. .Fluo. ratio was derived by dividing FITC-A/PE-Texas Red-A.

Additional information

A non-sigmoid component for L-asp uptake is detected at very high external concentrations (>10 mM L-asp) that cannot be blocked by the inhibitor TFB-TBOA, indicating additional uptake not mediated by SLC1A3).

Target data

SLC	SLC1A3
Synonyms	EA6, EAAT1, GLAST, GLAST1
SLC sub-family	SLC1
UniProt ID	P43003
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE029W-F (HEK293-JumpIn-TRex-SLC1A3-WTOE-p1)

Assay data

Dose response curve(s)	Compound name (1)	L-aspartic acid
	PubChem CID	5960
	Vendor (catalogue #)	

<p style="text-align: center;">HEK-SLC1A3 assy</p> <p>— L-asp +0.04% DMSO — L-asp +0.04% DMSO — L-asp +10uM TFB-TBOA — L-asp +10uM TFB-TBOA</p> <p>fluo. ratio (norm)</p> <p>[AA] / M</p>	<p>Mode of action</p> <p>EC50, IC50 (95% CI)</p>	<p>Substrate</p> <p>Curve 1: L-aspartic acid: 19 μM (17-21 μM) Curve 2: L-aspartic acid: 23 μM (21-26 μM)</p>
	<p>Compound name (2)</p>	<p>TFB-TBOA</p>
	<p>PubChem CID</p>	<p>52941382</p>
	<p>Vendor (catalogue #)</p>	
	<p>Mode of action</p>	<p>Inhibitor</p>
	<p>EC50, IC50 (95% CI)</p>	

Discussion

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).
- <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.04.537313>